

Issues and Challenges of Large Scale Pervasive Health Tele-Monitoring

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The use of information technology is already contributing in significant ways to the enhancement of healthcare delivery and improvement in quality of life for Canadians. However, the deployment of information technology has only scratched the surface of possibilities that new computer technologies, networking, and information science have to offer in the improvement of quality and cost-effectiveness of healthcare. There are many opportunities for enhancing wellness and healthcare where the once exotic notion of ubiquitous computing has become the norm. Patients and healthcare providers will soon have access to enormous sets of healthcare data provided by live non-invasive biometric sensors measuring many aspects of human physiology in action. Once collected to central servers using cloud technologies, this valuable health and wellness data must be analyzed and used for evidence-based healthcare, to stabilize physiology, to modify risky behaviors, and to telemonitor monitor our aging population or people with health challenges at home. The presentation will discuss the challenges associated to this technology including: system scalability of networks and cloud infrastructures, privacy, large scale data mining, and the integration of such systems in the Canadian healthcare system.

April 17, 2018